

Research

Role of standard chartered bank in community development in Bangladesh during Covid-19 pandemic

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Abstract: The covid-19 pandemic has affected the lives and livelihood of all sectors in Bangladesh. The Standard Chartered Bank in Bangladesh is one of those banks whose aim is to invest in community services and support equity and social causes. The bank has many contributions in the country's economy like- providing entrepreneurship programs, donating oxygen plants, creating employment for pandemic affected people, empowering rural areas, and providing emergency supports. The main function of SCB is to provide short term loans. Their another function is to support our garments industry. SCB provides foreign currency to support Bangladesh's EPZ. The purpose of this thesis is to review the role of Standard Chartered Bank in community development in Bangladesh during the Covid-19 Pandemic. The study has explored the depth and nature of Standard Chartered Banks Community Services in Bangladesh, their portfolio, their social works in Bangladesh, and their problems and risks before doing so. A constructive input and output model was prepared with the help of government data in order to ascertain objectivity. A two rating based survey were done among 20 participants to find out how satisfied people were with the community services of SCB during pandemic. According to the survey, 80% of respondents were satisfied with Standard Chartered Banks's community services, and according to the people, it helped the Bangladesh government a lot at the time of the pandemic. To do their functions correctly in the future, Standard Chartered bank must prepare lengthy resolutions, follow their stakeholders, and prepare proactive capital divination.

Keywords: Standard Chartered Bank, Covid-19, Bangladesh, Community Development, Donation

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1. Introduction

In the present world, people live their lives relying on banks to protect their money or lend money for their business. The banking sector of Bangladesh experienced a positive level of prosperity after liberation of Bangladesh. Bangladesh

Bank (BB) prosecuted many scheme policies to maintain bank governance, review banks' stability individually, and emphasize risk management. The banking sectors of Bangladesh are divided into four categories which are: SCB (State-owned Commercial Bank); DFI (State-owned Development Financial Institution); PCB (Private Commercial Bank); and FCB (Foreign Commercial Bank). Standard Chartered Bank in Bangladesh is a financial and banking service provider that aims to offer various banking services. It was Bangladesh's first largest foreign bank since 1905 (Standard Chartered, no date). Their services include deposit products, personal loans, credit cards, wealth management services, overdrafts, mortgages, and auto financing. Covid-19 was first detected in Bangladesh in March 2019 (Frontiers in Public Health, 2020). The Pandemic slowed down economic contractions and business activities. As a result, the banking sector of Bangladesh had fallen into irregularities of high-end loan payments and different scams, lack of corporate monitoring, escalation of loan recordings, sedation in loan recovery, and a decrease of capital. New challenges have risen for the coming future for the whole banking industry as the impacts of Covid-19 are increasing day by day. In this situation, Standard Chartered bank did not lack behind. They came forward to develop the society of Bangladesh with their community services. From health to women empowerment, from conducting environment change seminars to climate change seminars, from education services to research on Covid-19, they have done considerably for the society.

1.1. Aim and Scope

This thesis paper aims to review the role of Standard Chartered Bank in community development in Bangladesh during the Covid-19 Pandemic. SCB started its journey in Bangladesh in 1905 (Standard Chartered). Since then, the bank has made a lot of contributions to the society. The negative impact of Covid-19 is visible in the banks, Microcredit Institutions (MCI), Microfinance Institutions (MFI), NGOs, and SMEs. But SCB didn't give up. The conduction of SCB for the community and society development during the Pandemic was incomparable.

Unlike any other banks, SCB played a significant role in community service, but very little information has been researched on that. So this thesis aims to investigate the role of SCB in community development in Bangladesh during covid 19. On the other hand, this thesis paper also emphasizes the SCB generation in Bangladesh; such as: their banking profiles, their services in our rural communities, the problems and risks faced during the epidemic situation, and the responses of the Bangladesh government in providing the community services.

This thesis paper describes some ideas from an economic and financial point of view to measure the community developments done by Standard Chartered Bank at the time of Covid-19 in Bangladesh. The Pandemic has already affected the banking industry of Bangladesh. However, recovery cycles, length of invaded period, and the magnitude of impact are not the same for all banks. This is significant to gather knowledge from a feasible policy perspective. This report tries to discover the influence rate of Covid-19 in banking sectors, the benefactions done by SCB, their hardships while doing this, and the government's assistance. In particular, the study covers the SCB's adequacy, liquidity, asset quality, and profitability while doing the community work. The focal point of this research is Standard Chartered bank and their contribution to the society of Bangladesh, such as - SCB's portfolio, SCB's contribution in our GDP, and their community works in rural areas.

1.2. Research Question

While preparing this thesis, the research questions that arose about "Role of Standard Chartered Bank in community development in Bangladesh during Covid-19 pandemic" are given in the following:

- I. What are the impacts of Covid-19 on the banking industry of Bangladesh?
- II. What are the measures taken by SCB at the time of the epidemic to help the community?
- III. What are the services provided by SCB to rural communities?
- IV. What problems and does SCB faces risks during their services in the epidemic situation?

2. Research Methodology

This thesis draws on a combination of qualitative and quantitative data. The qualitative analysis is based on Standard Chartered Banks's financial and economic operations, community services, lending, and impacts on the Bangladesh's GDP. Bangladesh government applied a stable economic design tool by conducting a social-economical casting. SCBs induced, direct and indirect effects on total revenues and employment (the cost of total sold goods will be eliminated) were accessed by us to quantify the data. It should also be underlined that this thesis is an image based on the Covid-19 pandemic in Bangladesh and Standard Chartered Banks' contribution to their community development.

A constructive input and output model was prepared (a model of the total GDPs after the effect of Covid-19) with the help of government data in order to ascertain objectivity. When illustrating the SCB's community services at the time of the pandemic, full cautiousness was maintained to not to overestimate any pieces of information.

Two rating-based surveys were done. It includes six questionnaires, three options, and twenty participants. Here they had to mark the appropriate answer based on their experience. The questions were:

Questions	Options
1. At Covid-19 SCBs, community development services were for a good cause in Bangladesh.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Satisfied. ● Not Satisfied. ● Less Satisfied. ● No Comments
2. The Bangladesh government helped with Standard Chartered Bank's community services during the pandemic.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Satisfied. ● Not Satisfied. ● Less Satisfied. ● No Comments
3. Standard Chartered Bank has contributed to the GDP and job sector of Bangladesh.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Satisfied. ● Not Satisfied. ● Less Satisfied. ● No Comments
4. The bank provided all sorts of health supports to the rural people.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Satisfied. ● Not Satisfied. ● Less Satisfied. ● No Comments

5. The donations Standard Chartered Bank provided was very helpful.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Satisfied. ● Not Satisfied. ● Less Satisfied. ● No Comments
6. Standard Chartered Bank claims, "We are Here for Good." Are you satisfied with their service?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Satisfied. ● Not Satisfied. ● Less Satisfied. ● No Comments

Table 1: The questionnaire

3. Pre and Post Covid Status of Banking Industry in Bangladesh

3.1. Pre Covid-Status of Banking Industry

In a country, the banking industry is considered the lifeline of its economic structure. Banks play an influential role in supporting and initiating economic and financial prosperity in a developing country like Bangladesh. It has passed a long period and witnessed the growth of businesses, capital parallelism, and asset attribution.

The banking industry in Bangladesh is confined to slow automation, medium use of internet banking, and minor accomplishment in retail banking. Despite all these reasons, the banking industry of Bangladesh is doing well in the retail business. As per "Global Competitiveness Report 2019," Bangladesh ranked 130th and scored 38.3 among banks from different countries (Abu Afsarul Haider, 2020). The total CAR (Capital Adequacy Ratio) is 11.60% (Abu Afsarul Haider, 2020).

In 2017 the liquidity ratio of our banking industry was 56.900%; in 2018, it was 48.400%, and in 2019 it was 29.700% (CEIC, 1997-2019).

3.2. Post-Covid Status of Banking Industry

Due to Covid-19, Bangladesh's banking sector fell by around BDT 18.2 billion in default loans and had to face 9% of NPL (Non-Performing Loan) in March 2020 (Tarik N. A. et.al., 2020). Due to the scarcity of credit guarantees, banks had limitations in providing corporate loans. During the pandemic, Bangladesh Bank started working with the world bank to induce the potential losses and started USD 300 million credit guarantee schemes (Tarik N. A. et.al., 2020).

On 3rd July, Bangladesh Bank ordered other private and government banks to clear all their incentive funds within August. In December 2019, the total capital of the banking industry was around BDT 236 billion (Tarik N. A. et.al., 2020). Due to the economic crisis caused by Covid-19, the banking capital of Bangladesh was getting low, which caused a short-term NPL.

4. Standard Chartered Bank in Bangladesh

4.1. SCB in Bangladesh

The Chartered Bank is a foreign private bank that started its operation in Bangladesh in 1948 (History of Standard Chartered Bank, No Date). Their first branch was in Chittagong. The purpose behind opening their first branch was post-war restructuring and expansion in South Asian countries. The bank opened its second branch in Dhaka in 1966

and announced it as its main headquarter (History of Standard Chartered Bank, No Date). It merged with the Standard Bank and changed its name to Standard Chartered Bank in 1969 (History of Standard Chartered Bank, No Date).

Currently, there are 26 branches and 97 ATMs, employing more than 17,000 people in Bangladesh. Now, SCB is operating in 6 cities: Dhaka, Khulna, Chittagong, Sylhet, Narayanganj, and Bogura (Banksbd.org, No Date). Their primary services are- Priority Banking, Islamic Banking, Personal Banking, Business, Green Banking, and Corporate Institutional Banking.

Through its business model, Standard Chartered bank comprises all of its markets to achieve full sustainability. Their approach depends on three priorities; such as: subscribing to Sustainable GDP, being an Accountable Company, and exercising community works. The bank has efficiency in finance and responsibility to support the job creation and economic growth of Bangladesh. Having a robust corporate regime, the bank generates a suitable workplace for all the employees, and minimizes work pressure which makes the bank a responsible industry. SCB bank's involvement in community programs and voluntary positions promotes positive economic and social outcomes.

5.2. Awards of SCB in Bnagladesh

Year	Awards
2016	Best Foreign Bank
2017	Best Asiamoney Digital Bank
2016, 2017 and 2018	Triple A Awards
2010, 2012, 2013, 2014, 2015 and 2017	Bank of the Year
2009, 2010, 2011, 2012, 2013, 2014, 2016, 2017 and 2018	Best Foreign Bank
2018	Best Foreign Investment Bank
2016	Best Foreign Exchange Bank
2017 and 2018	Best CSR Bank
2017 and 2018	Best Islamic Digital Bank
2016	Deal of the Year
2017	Islamic Banking Window
2012, 2013 and 2014	Best Corporate Performance Award

Table 2: Awards of Standard Chartered Bank in Bangladesh

Source: <https://www.sc.com/bd/about-us/>

5.3. "Seeing is Believing" Program

Standard Chartered Bank's flagship community project, 'Seeing is Believing', started its journey in Bangladesh. Under this project, they built a children's ward and operation theatre at Islamia Eye Hospital. Under this program they can provide eye treatment to around 12,000 every year (Standard Chartered, n d). By 2018, SCB had provided eye screening treatment worth 67,475 takas to 1,218,702 individuals (Standard Chartered, n d). Amongst them, 106,313 people received refractive corrective services (Standard Chartered, n d). The bank trained around 8000 ophthalmologists and eye care nurses to do this.

Standard Chartered Bank is also working to alleviate blindness for the poor rural communities in coastal areas. The bank provides eye screening, cataract surgery and eye care services under the Rangdhanu Friendship Hospital. They have served more than 4300 patients and treated 400 preventable blindness by providing the sight-restoring operation (Standard Chartered, n d).

5.4. Wholesale Banking

SCB is one of the highest contributors to wholesale banking in our country. The yearly turnover is more than USD 25 million in wholesale banking. SCB provides cash management, finance, capital- risking, foreign exchange, securities, corporate finance solutions, and risk management services to their clients (international and local corporates), development organizations, and government institutions. Standard Chartered Bank in Bangladesh also serves critical goods imports and services (machinery, crude oil, and commodities). Moreover, SCB disposes of syndicated flexibility on the international leveraging and markets by its lending.

5.5. Consumer Banking

Standard Chartered Bank has 280,000 retail customers served through their 20 express bank centers, nine booths, 19 branches, and 90 ATMs all over Bangladesh (Ethan B Kapstein and Dr Rene Kim, No Date). The bank also provides online banking and call centre facilities. SCB's most important products are credit cards, savings, personal loans, current accounts, auto loans, mortgages, and term deposits. SCB also has many Shariah-compliant products sold under Saadiq (a global brand).

The bank identifies SMEs (Small and Medium Size Enterprise) as companies with USD 25 million in turnovers, including 15000 customers. 30% of consumer banking depends on loan books (Ethan B Kapstein and Dr Rene Kim, No Date). Standard Chartered Bank owned 'Retail Financial Services' in 2012 and was recognized as 'Best Retail Bank in Bangladesh'.

5.6. Sustainable Finance

Standard Chartered Bank is recognized for its potential financing decisions, which impact the people, society and environment all over the country. The bank owns 14 statemental positions in high economic sectors like- child labour, gas and oil, forestry and mining, water, and climate change. The assertion sets out the social and environmental standards. The bank's sustainable finance program helps the employee to identify their proposed mitigating keys and risk identification early. SCB also pledges to provide clean finance technology globally with USD 8.4 billion (by the end of 2011).

6. Discussion

6.1. Standard Chartered Bank in community development in Bangladesh during the Covid-19 pandemic

The global economy has put into intense exigence due to Covid-19. It will not be counted as a regular pandemic but will be considered a result of financial disaster in the microeconomic sectors of Bangladesh. The pandemic has bought inversion in Bangladesh's health, GDP, and social well-being sectors. Due to Covid-19, Bangladesh's GDP fell to 3.5% (2020) from 8.2% (2019) (Asian Development Bank, 2021). But the banking sector didn't give up, and they had done everything to fight this situation.

Standard Chartered Bank in Bangladesh is one of those banks that stands straight to fight against Covid-19. From proving funds to making enough resources, the bank had done everything from their end. Recently SCB has been awarded as 'Best CSR Bank' and 'Best Bank in Covid-19 Initiatives' at BT Banking award in 2020 (Star Business Report, 2021). In this remark, CEO of SCB Naser Ezaz Bijoy stated, "In the face of a pandemic that will mark an era, the need of the hour has always been to protect both lives and livelihoods." (Star Business Report, 2021).

This bank aims to support lives and livelihoods during this pandemic. In 2021, SCB had announced a 13.5 crore worth strategic action plan in response to Covid-19 (Star Business Report, 2021). The main target of this donation is to support health care, food and the economy. To qualify long term recovery, SCB is working with UCEP Bangladesh to help the economically unprivileged people.

This chapter will focus on the Standard Chartered Banks' community development services during the epidemic.

Image 1: SCB's Covid-19 Response in community development in Bangladesh.

Source: <https://www.thedailystar.net/business/news/standard-chartered-bangladesh-wins-best-bank-covid-19-initiatives-and-best-csr-bank-awards-2138326>

Converting Migrants into Entrepreneurs- Standard Chartered Bank and BRAC Bank had declared an economic self-reliable initiative for migrant workers. The title of the project was "Covid-19 recovery: Entrepreneurship Training and Gainful Employment for Returnee Migrants". It was a two years project (Star Business Desk, 2022). This project will provide entrepreneurship training, emergency arrival facilitation and counselling to the migrants. Preference will be given to youths from 18-35 years to women with weak demographics and three main city ports (Dhaka, Chittagong, and Comilla).

Donating Oxygen Plant- Standard Chartered Bank provided oxygen generation plant to Maa-O-Shishu General Hospital in Chittagong (bdnews24.com, 2022). The plants can provide 1700 litres oxygen in a minute, and each will provide 436 litres per minute (bdnews24.com, 2022). According to the CEO of Standard Chartered Bank, Naser Ezaz Bijoy, "Throughout the challenges faced during the pandemic at Standard Chartered, the bank has made its mission to stand beside communities across Bangladesh, supporting both lives and livelihood with a range of interventions" (bdnews24.com, 2022). The donation had helped a lot to maintain the Covid-19 unit at the time of the epidemic.

Suitable workplace for the Pandemic Affected People- Standard Chartered Bank and UCEP inaugurated employment reintegration and re-skilling program for financially and economically atrophied people who lost their jobs due to the pandemic (SCB Media Release, 2020). To Covid-19, Bangladesh's economy faced structural and fundamental changes during the recovery. Under this initiative program, an assessment study will be conducted by UCEP to identify formal and informal skill gaps. After that, based on the assessment result, a training program will be provided to the skilled vulnerable people.

Donation for the Covid 19 Affected Patients- Standard Chartered Bank has enacted a coronavirus epicentre for Covid-19 patients in Narayanganj. The bank has promised to pay the half daily treatment cost of 80 Covid-19 patients at the Narayanganj SAJIDA Hospital. Previously the bank had provided the diurnal treatment cost of 40 viruses affected patients at the same hospital (SCB Media Release, 2020). SCB aimed to serve 5,000 Covid-19 patients with the help of this foundation.

Empowering Urban Communities- Standard Chartered Bank and SAJIDA Foundation came forward to help the extreme poverty communities with their job placements, provide employable skills, and offer business development training. The first stage of this initiative will support 300 beneficiaries from Dhaka, Chandpur and Chittagong. According to the SAJIDA Foundation, around 77.5% of people had lost their jobs, and 41.9% had no money for their treatment (SCB Press Release, 2021). So, this empowering program was for these people who have no money or no job.

Donating for Emergency Reliefs- Standard Chartered Bank had contributed USD 1.6 million to UNICEF and Red Cross programs to provide emergency relief to the COVID-affected community (SCB Press Release, 2020). According to Naser Ezaz Bijoy (the CEO of SCB), *"By working with these organizations, we can support the delivery of rapid and effective emergency relief that aims to address some of the key challenges created by the COVID-19 pandemic."* (SCB Press Release, 2020). The purpose behind this donation was to provide secondary and primary health care support, protective communication measures, providing personal protection equipment (PPE), and distribution of hygiene products and food.

Emergency Supports- Standard Chartered Bank in Bangladesh had collaborated with BRAC to provide an emergency package to 25000 people; there were 5000 low-income families in lockdown areas (Press Release, 2020). According to

Asif Saleh, Executive Director, BRAC, said, "We are glad to join forces with Standard Chartered and stand beside vulnerable families under lockdown with essential food support." (Standard Chartered, 2020)

7. Standard Chartered Bank's Other Contributions- A Qualitative Study

7.1. SCB's Contribution to Our GDP

Standard Chartered Banks' term loans help to raise Bangladesh's local economy. The impact of trade loans or short term loans is not as significant as banks' other operations. Today, SCB's value-added contribution to the GDP of Bangladesh is around 1.1%. On the other hand, the Standard Chartered Bank facilitated 3.3% of government tax receipts (Ethan B Kapstein and Dr Rene Kim, No Date). The bank, directly and indirectly, supports the government's tax payments, which are around USD 253 million and approximately 3.3% of total tax receipts (Ethan B Kapstein and Dr Rene Kim, No Date).

Figure 1: SCB's Value-added generation.

Source: <https://av.sc.com/corp-en/content/docs/bangladesh-social-and-economic-impact-study.pdf>

In Figure 1, it can be seen that SCB's total value-added generation is USD 1,177 Million. Term loans and trade loans together contribute USD 1071 million to onshore finance.

7.2. Contribution to Job Sector

Standard Chartered Bank provides around 0.6% of employment in Bangladesh's economy. The bank has about 1,189 full-time staff (Ethan B Kapstein and Dr Rene Kim, No Date). Including all branches and their teams, the bank has approximately 466000 jobs in Bangladesh's economy (Ethan B Kapstein and Dr Rene Kim, No Date).

On the other hand, SCB's lending procedure supports business loans which also helps to create employment in Bangladesh. In particular, long term financial loans allow clients to expand their business. Standard Chartered Bank provides around USD 1 million yearly as term loans, facilitating 484 jobs in the market (Ethan B Kapstein and Dr Rene Kim, No Date). SCB supports the most intensive sectors like the garments industry, wholesale and retail, and agriculture in Bangladesh.

Client Segment	Economy Based on Employment (USD 1 Million-Number of Jobs)
Consumer Banking	340
SMEs	1203
Commodity Traders and Agriculture	571
Trade Finance	153
Local Corporates	389

Table 3: SCB's Financing 1 Million on Employment

7.3. Supporting Garment Sector

Standard Chartered Bank has always supported the garments industry of Bangladesh. The bank has conducted its operation for five years in Chittagong, investing in their EPZ. The bank has provided foreign currency to this sector to help in their balancing between extensive global work and currency liquidity. As of 2020, 37,400 jobs have been provided through banks providing loans to the garments industry (Ethan B Kapstein and Dr Rene Kim, No Date). Most of the trade financing is supported by SCB's non-monetary finance products and letters of credit. These type of services helps garment products to sell their products in the international market.

	Bangladesh Total	Total Supported by SCB	Monetarily Support
Garments Export	USD 18 Billion	5.6%	1.0%
Garments Import	USD 7 Billion	6.9%	1.2%
Total Trade	USD 25 Billion	12.6%	2.2%

Table 4: Standard Chartered Banks' Contribution

Source: <https://av.sc.com/corp-en/content/docs/bangladesh-social-and-economic-impact-study.pdf>

7.4. Supporting Entrepreneurs

Standard Chartered Bank considers entrepreneurs as an integral part of the rise of the finance and future growth of the economy in Bangladesh. The bank has always supported women and entrepreneurs. In 2011, SCB signed a contract with the Bangladesh Federation of Women Entrepreneurs (BFWE) to support the women business owners by providing a training program (Ethan B Kapstein and Dr Rene Kim, No Date). The training was provided to 20 women and conducted by a contractor. SCB declared their first women based program in February 2012.

7.5. Aiding Microfinance Institution

Bangladesh is considered a single market in Standard Chartered Bank's international business. The bank provides funds to many microfinance institutions like- BURO (Basic Unit for Resource and Opportunities), BRAC, the Shakti Foundation for Disadvantaged Women, and TMSS (Thenga Mara Mohila Sabuj Sangha) in the country. Over the last five years, Standard Chartered has provided 34% of loans to MFIs, mainly agriculture-based MFIs, which benefited 2.3 million people in the country (Ethan B Kapstein and Dr Rene Kim, No Date).

7.6. Funding Financial Institution

Standard Chartered Bank's a trade and term loan to Financial Institutions (FIs). The total output is around USD 430 million, about 0.4% of GDP (Ethan B Kapstein and Dr Rene Kim, No Date).

7.7. Off-Shore Financing

As a global bank, Standard Chartered facilitates the business sectors of Bangladesh, such as the telecom and power sectors. Both these sectors require investment based off-shore financing in capital intensive projects, and SCB's off-shore financing is approximately one-fifth of Bangladesh's total foreign investment.

For the last few years, SCB has supported improving power access in Bangladesh by serving them with financing contractors, power generation sectors, and others. As of 31st December 2011, the bank has helped produce 1,156 MW of electricity, which is around 24% of Bangladesh's power capacity (Ethan B Kapstein and Dr Rene Kim, No Date).

Information and Communication Technology (ICT) is essential for the economic growth of Bangladesh. SCB's off-shore capital has played an important role in Bangladesh's telecom infrastructure. The bank has increased telecom finance by 67% since December 2008 (Ethan B Kapstein and Dr Rene Kim, No Date).

7.8. Skill Development and Human Resource

Through training and recruitment programs, Standard Chartered Bank has efficiently influenced Bangladesh's financial system. From clinging to vital financing programs of diversity to recruit the best candidates, the bank sets a graceful example to the society of Bangladesh (Regardless their gender or background). SCB provide leading-edge training to their employees, which will help them to work in another institute.

8.Result and Analysis

In the survey mentioned in the methodology, there were six questions. These are:

- I. At Covid-19 SCBs, community development services were for a good cause in Bangladesh.
- II. The Bangladesh government helped with Standard Chartered Banks's community services during the pandemic.
- III. Standard Chartered Bank has contributed to the GDP and job sector of Bnagladesh.
- IV. The bank provided all sorts of health supports to the rural people.
- V. The donations Standard Chartered Bank provided was very helpful.
- VI. Standard Chartered Bank claims, "We are Here for Good." Are you satisfied with their service?

The options were 'Satisfied,' 'Not Satisfied,' 'Less Satisfied' and 'No Comments'.

Figure 2: The survey on SCB Community service

Source: created by the author

These questions were asked to twenty people. The result is, for **Question I**, 15 people chose the 'Satisfied' option, 2 people chose 'Not Satisfied', 2 people chose the 'Less Satisfied' option and 1 participant chose 'No Comments'. For **Question II**, 10 people chose the 'Satisfied' option, 5 people chose 'Not Satisfied', 3 people chose 'Less Satisfied' and 2 participants chose 'No Comments' option. For **Question III**, 12 people chose the 'Satisfied' option, 3 people chose 'Not Satisfied', 3 people chose 'Less Satisfied' and 2 participants chose 'No Comments' option. For **Question IV**, 13 people chose the 'Satisfied' option, 4 people chose 'Not Satisfied', 3 people chose 'Less Satisfied' option. For **Question V**, 16 people chose the 'Satisfied' option, 4 people chose 'Less Satisfied' option. For **Question VI**, 15 people chose the 'Satisfied' option, and 5 participants chose 'No Comments' option.

So, 80% of respondents were satisfied with Standard Chartered Bank's community services, and according to them, it helped the Bangladesh government a lot at the time of the pandemic.

8.1. Services Provided by SCB to Rural Communities

Standard Chartered Bank is working in Bangladesh with a commitment to serve their best services to promote economic and social development. The bank believes in inclusive growth by introducing innovative schemes and programs. Bitopi Das Chowdhury, head of corporate affairs of Standard Chartered Bank, stated that "Standard Chartered stands by our communities," and we are "Here for good" (The Business Standard, 2022).

According to Bitopi Das Chowdhury, to provide better services in rural communities, Standard Chartered Bank focuses on the following six keys (The Business Standard, 2022):

- ❖ **Food and Hygiene:** Standard Chartered Bank provides life-saving food and safe hygiene to 240,000 people through Kumudini Welfare Trust, BRAC, and Bidyanondo. (Standard Chartered Media Release, 2020). On the other hand, the bank has also served more than 7,000,000 foods and constructed personal hygiene tools.

- ❖ **Health care:** Till 2020, Standard Chartered Bank has provided 14 days of health support to 740 critical patients. The bank has recently donated medical oxygen generation plants in three rural community hospitals with high volume installed capacity. These oxygen plants can support around 400 patients per day. In this program, Bidyanondo and Sajida Foundation helped them (Standard Chartered Media Release, 2020).
- ❖ **Education:** Standard Chartered Bank had contributed BDT 109,135,000 (USD 1.3 million) to UNICEF for our education. The primary purpose of this donation was to provide education in remote areas and to protect women's education. In rural communities, SCB has provided education to 4000 children.
- ❖ **Supporting Frontliners:** SCB had contributed BDT 25,185,000 (USD 300,000) to Red Cross programs to help the frontliners in rural areas.
- ❖ **Beneficiaries for the poor:** To support economic reintegration and livelihood in the long term, SCB donated 1700 beneficiaries to economically vulnerable people with business development training, providing jobs and technical skills.
- ❖ **Supporting Livelihood:** Standard Chartered Bank had helped 2000 farmers by providing them with 200 tons of farming tools and delivered 200000 beneficiaries free of cost. The Ovizatrik foundation had helped them in this process ((Standard Chartered Media Release, 2020)).

8.2. The Problems and Risks Faced by SCB during Services in the Epidemic Situation

The global economy has fallen due to Covid-19, which results in the shutdown of businesses and the slowdown of economic contractions. As a result, the banking industry of Bangladesh had to face a lack of governance, a rise in the loan write-offs, gradual loan recovery, irregularities, scams, shortfall of capital, and elevation of non-performing loans. Standard Chartered Bank in Bangladesh is no exception. The bank also had to face the same things. Despite doing many community services, the bank had to face the following risks and problems during Covid-19:

- **The downfall of Financial Operations-** Standard Chartered bank had to face the failure of financial operations. As per the Bangladesh Bureau of Statistics, in 2020, SCBs financial intercession was drastically falling.
- **Covid-affected bankers-** As per Bangladesh Bank (BB) statistics, approximately 27,237 bankers were affected, and 143 bankers died due to Covid-19, where 2% were from Standard Chartered Bank (Tapash Chandra Paul, No Date).
- **Poor NPL Condition-** NPL volume (Non-Performing Loans) was growing day by day from January 2020 to March 2021 (Tapash Chandra Paul, No Date). Due to this reason, Standard Chartered Bank had low asset quality for high volume NPL and downcast profitability conditions.
- **Low Liquidity-** Usually, all the banks want to have enough liquidity to provide loans and make payments. But due to Covid-19, SCB was facing a low quantity of liquidity.

8.3. The Responses of the Bangladesh Government in Providing the Community Services by SCB

During the pandemic Covid-19, Standard Chartered Bank stood by the Bengali community and helped the Bangladeshi people as much as they could. SCB donated large sums of money, built hospitals, provided oxygen generation, and created health awareness. As a result, the Bangladesh government was very grateful to this bank. Standard Chartered Bank was awarded as 'Best CSR Bank' and later 'Best Bank in Covid-19 Initiatives' by the Bangladesh government.

Naser Ezaz Bijoy, CEO of Standard Chartered Bangladesh, stated, "In the face of a pandemic that will mark an era, the need of the hour has always been to protect both lives and livelihoods" (The Daily Star, 2022).

On the other hand, different government organizations like Kumudini Welfare Trust, BRAC, Sajida, Oviatrik, and Bidyanondo foundation stood by their good deeds (The Business Standard, 2022).

9. Conclusion

Since its independence, Bangladesh has ejected from poverty and was announced as "a model for poverty reduction" by The World Bank in 2020 (Asif Saleh, 2022). Bangladesh achieved a high accrescent GDP from 2010-2020 and is predicted to be a developed country by 2041 (Asif Saleh, 2020). The Global North had dictated and designed the decision-makers to approach the traditional development fairly uni-directional worldwide. But in 2019, Covid-19, Known as Coronavirus, hit hard and spoiled all these years' economic and financial outcomes. The Covid-19 pandemic has caused a colossal level of financial and economic crisis. Over the last three to four years, banks were the only source of elasticity in the middle of economic unrest.

Standard Chartered Bank is the largest and oldest foreign bank in Bangladesh. At Covid-19, the bank had a remarkable impact on Bangladesh's economic progression and community advancement. This thesis paper is based on 'how Standard Chartered Bank stands with Bangladesh at the time of Covid-19 for the progression and development of our community.' Standard Chartered in Bangladesh is one of those banks that tried their heart and soul to fight this pandemic.

The following steps of Covid-19 pandemic challenges have already started for global banks like Standard Chartered. There are many debates about managing the opportunities and challenges to cope with the situation. The 'New Normal' is the new term to fix our capital structure. In the following, there has been given some solicitations which can help The Standard Chartered Bank in development services:

Focus on the Lengthy Resolutions: Firstly, Standard Chartered Bank must start its plans, keeping future schemes in mind. Before beginning a new capital allocation structure, it is essential to focus on the long-term business technical objects. Nevertheless, with the remaining uncertainties about the economic recovery, financial swiftness stays paramount.

Secondly, Standard Chartered Banks's corporate functions requires more monitoring than their present monitoring system. Mainly, the bank should focus on how has the sector worked since the pandemic and have to revise the 2007-08 financial collapse solutions. Also, SCB has to think about whether these changes are sustainable or not.

Understand Bank and Stakeholders Prospects- Standard Chartered Bank should respect its shareholders and competence. The bank should also stature the market perceptions and their overall changed structures. For example, gas and oil had the highest consumer products for the last fifteen years. It still suffers in return based on its total due in the past decades. It is caused by environmental emergence and radical volatility.

On the other hand, Standard Chartered Bank has been confident in raising the stock market resolutely.

Emersion in their Debt Level- Standard Chartered Bank's corporate debt level had collapsed due to a worldwide economic and financial crisis that had harmed all sectors. According to Earnings Before Interest, Taxes, Depreciation, and Amortization (EBITDA) ratios, the debt level of world-famous companies was 2.3x average in 2019 (Shoaib Yaqub, 2020).

Day by day, the indebtedness of world-famous banks is rising without any investor backlash. So, SCB should balance their debt level to keep their community services.

Satisfactory Capital Divination- Standard Chartered Bank in Bangladesh should focus on being more proactive and opportunistic. The bank should prepare a balance sheet based on reinforcement headroom to do this. Standard Chartered Bank has to add the 'Self Help' option to do this. It can help to generate skilled use of their capital. Then, it requires a reconsideration of the long-term wholesale capital structure.

If Standard Chartered Bank can successfully apply the 'Self Help' scheme, they can directly control reduced capital consumption and cost optimizations.

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10. References

- [1] Standard Chartered Bank (No date) BanksBD.org. Retrieved From: <https://www.banksbd.org/scb>
- [2] ADB (2021 December 22) 'ADB Helps Bangladesh on Road to Recovery from COVID-19' Asian Development Bank. Retrieved From: <https://www.adb.org/results/adb-helps-bangladesh-road-recovery-covid-19#:~:text=Bangladesh%27s%20GDP%20fell%20sharply%20in,in%20wake%20of%20the%20pandemic>
- [3] Assignment Point (No date) 'History of Standard Chartered Bank' Assignment Point. Retrieved From: <https://assignmentpoint.com/history-of-standard-chartered-bank/>
- [4] Bangladesh Bank, (1997-2019) "Bangladesh Banking Sector: Liquidity Ratio" CEIC. Retrieved From: <https://www.ceicdata.com/en/bangladesh/banking-sector-liquidity-ratio>
- [5] Bangladesh Bank. (2021 July) "Covid-19 Pandemic in Bangladesh: Policy Responses and its Impact". Available at https://www.bb.org.bd/pub/special//covid19_06072021.pdf
- [6] BD24 News Desk (2022 March 3) 'Standard Chartered Bank donates Bangladesh's first oxygen plant to Chattogram hospital' bdnews24.Com. Retrieved From: <https://bdnews24.com/bangladesh/2022/03/03/standard-chartered-bank-donates-bangladesh-s-first-oxygen-plant-to-chattogram-hospital>

- [7] Ghosh R. and Saima F.N (2021 January 9) "Resilience of commercial banks of Bangladesh to the shocks caused by COVID-19 pandemic: an application of MCDM-based approaches." Asian Journal of Accounting Research
- [8] Haider A. A. (2020 July 26) "A strong banking system makes a strong economy" The Daily Star. Retrieved From: <https://www.thedailystar.net/opinion/news/strong-banking-system-makes-strong-economy-1936077>
- [9] Kapstein E.B and Kim R. (No Date) "The Social and Economic Impact of Standard Chartered in Bangladesh". Standard Chartered Bank. Retrieved from: <https://av.sc.com/corp-en/content/docs/bangladesh-social-and-economic-impact-study.pdf>
- [10] Khatun M.N., Mitra S. and Sarkar N.I. (2021 July) "Mobile banking during COVID-19 pandemic in Bangladesh: A novel mechanism to change and accelerate people's financial access" Research Gate
- [11] Knudson J. (2021, November/December) "How Community Banks Survived the COVID Pandemic" ProQuest. Retrieved From: <https://www.proquest.com/openview/fe8a4add437078b3ed0ee115c5e8d035/1?pq-origsite=gscholar&cbl=47754>
- [12] Kozlakidis Z., Shamsuzzaman and Hasan K. (2020 April 30) 'COVID-19 and Bangladesh: Challenges and How to Address Them' Frontiers in Public Health. Retrieved From: <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fpubh.2020.00154/full>
- [13] Mohammad K.U. and Khan M.R. (2021 December 29) "Bank Capital Structure Dynamics and Covid-19: Evidence from South Asia" iRASD Journal of Economics
- [14] Mondal T. (2020) "Customer satisfaction on customer service of IFIC Bank limited" An internship report submitted to the BBS in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree of BBA
- [15] Paul C. T., "COVID-19 Impact in Banking Industry" Retrieved From: <https://mblbd.com/assets/corporate/senior/COVID-19-Impact-in-Banking-Industry.pdf>
- [16] Ramasamy K. (2020) "Impact Analysis in Banking, Insurance and Financial services industry due to COVID-19 Pandemic" Pramana Research Journal
- [17] Reza F., Kawsar E. and Mahabub T.B. (2020 April 9) "COVID-19 impact and responses: Bangladesh" Build Bangladesh
- [18] Saleh A. (2022 January 18) "Development needs to change. Bangladesh can show us how" World Economic Forum. Retrieved From: <https://www.weforum.org/agenda/2022/01/development-needs-change-bangladesh-can-show-us-how/>
- [19] SCB (2020 December 6) 'Standard Chartered and UCEP Bangladesh partner to help build a future fit workforce to support rapid Covid-19 recovery' Standard Chartered Media Release
- [20] SCB (2020 July 6) 'Standard Chartered pledges further assistance to COVID-19 patients in Narayanganj' Standard Chartered Media Release
- [21] SCB (2020 May 16) 'Standard Chartered and BRAC to deliver essential food items to 5000 low-income families facing COVID-19 lock-down' Standard Chartered Press Release
- [22] SCB (2020 May 31) 'Standard Chartered Bangladesh contributes USD 1.6 million for COVID-19 emergency relief' Standard Chartered Press Release
- [23] SCB (2021 February 23) 'Standard Chartered and SAJIDA Foundation to empower urban communities below extreme poverty line with employable skills, job placements and entrepreneurship/business development support' Standard Chartered Press Release
- [24] Standard Chartered Bank. 'Overview' Retrieved From: <https://www.sc.com/bd/> Accessed on May22, 2022

- [25] Standard Chartered Media Releases, (2020 December 6) "Standard Chartered and UCEP Bangladesh partner to help build a future fit workforce to support rapid Covid-19 recovery". Standard Chartered. Retrieved From: <https://av.sc.com/bd/content/docs/bd-sc-and-ucep-bangladesh-partnership.pdf>
- [26] Star Business Desk (2021 July 26) 'StanChart, Brac to turn returnee migrants into entrepreneurs' The Daily Star. Retrieved From: <https://www.thedailystar.net/business/economy/banks/news/stanchart-brac-turn-returnee-migrants-entrepreneurs-2137051>
- [27] Tarik N. A., Ahmed S., Niamatullah S., and Ahmed T. (2020 July 8) "Bangladesh Banking Sector Report The COVID Crisis Poses A Historic Challenge To Banks - Only The Most Agile Will Survive" AT Capital Bangladesh Banking Sector Report. Retrieved From: <https://www.arx.cfa/-/media/regional/arx/post-pdf/2020/07/11/at-capital-bangladesh-banking-sector-report.ashx?la=en&hash=1EC1487BDA3DAD98B7BB963126441A541915F388>
- [28] The Business Standard, (2022 March 8) "Standard Chartered stands by our communities: Bitopi Das Chowdhury." The Business Standard. Retrieved From: <https://www.tbsnews.net/interviews/standard-chartered-stands-our-communities-bitopi-das-chowdhury-381607>
- [29] The Daily Star, (2021 July 27) "Standard Chartered Bangladesh wins 'Best Bank in Covid-19 Initiatives' and 'Best CSR Bank' awards" The Daily Star. Retrieved From: <https://www.thedailystar.net/business/news/standard-chartered-bangladesh-wins-best-bank-covid-19-initiatives-and-best-csr-bank-awards-2138326>
- [30] Yaqub S. (2020 July 21) "Beyond the COVID-19 shock: revisiting capital allocation" Standard Chartered. Retrieved From: <https://www.sc.com/en/feature/beyond-the-covid-19-shock-revisiting-capital-allocation/>

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